

Custom Nortek Signature ADCP Synchronization Controller a.k.a. “Trigger Board”

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Introduction

It is often desirable to mount several ADCPs on a platform – e.g., to provide upward/downward beam orientation (Fig. 1). In these cases, the ADCPs need to be *synchronized* to avoid cross-talk contamination of observations.

Nortek Signature ADCPs provide means to both send and receive synchronization pulses (TTL or RS485) or serial synchronization commands.

There are several important limitations:

1) Nortek synchronization scheme makes the ADCPs ping synchronously (Fig. 2). This avoids transmit/receive interference (which is important), but not necessarily interference of reflected pings.

2) Nortek scheme only works when ping schedule is exactly the same for both ADCPs, in that the same type of pings (broadband [LR] vs. pulse-coherent [HR] vs. echosounder) are issued at the same time. The reason for this is that HR/LR pings have very different transmit pulse length, so we get transmit/receive interference even when the pings start at the same time. It is

Fig. 1 REMUS 100 Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (left) and Lagrangian Float (right) each equipped with two Nortek Signature1000 ADCPs.

Fig. 2 An example of typical ping sequence of two Nortek Signature1000 ADCPs using default synchronization scheme. This illustration shows the second instrument missing a ping (“X”) which leads to dyssynchronization of subsequent pings.

expected that identical setup of the two ADCPs would be enough to ensure that the ping schedule remains uniform. However, this is not the case: If one of the ADCPs encounters an interruption, the schedules can “slide” relative to each other (see illustration in Fig. 2).

3) Ping-to-ping delays are hard-wired for a particular sampling scheme. There appears to be a desire to “cluster” the pings in time (Fig. 2), so minimal intervals as short as 1/16th of a second are common. Such short intervals lead to previous-ping interference at certain distances from the surface/bottom (around $\frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{16} c \approx 47\text{m}$).

These limitations are inherent in Nortek’s approach to synchronization and ping scheduling. They cannot be fully mitigated by altering the instrument’s setup.

An alternative solution is to provide the ADCPs with independent trigger pulses, managed by a dedicated microcontroller (MCU). In the “ideal” synchronization scheme (Fig. 3), we would want to

- 1) Allow independent triggering of the ADCPs. This would allow full deconflicting of the pings.
- 2) Make the ping schedule(s) more flexible, allowing the two ADCPs to have different number of pings during each one-second interval.
- 3) Allow more flexibility in ping intervals to avoid previous-ping interference.
- 4) Ensure that two ADCPs start sampling at the same time regardless of when they were initialized. This would facilitate synchronization of ADCP clocks.
- 5) Open the possibility for synchronization of *more than two* ADCPs or synchronization with other sonars.

To achieve this and provide synchronization of two Nortek Signature1000 ADCPs on a Mixed-Layer Lagrangian Float (MLF), a STM32-based “Trigger Board” was developed for NSF Anisotropy project.

Fig. 3 An example of desired ping sequence of two Nortek Signature1000 ADCPs using custom “Trigger Board”. Note increased pin-to-ping intervals (1/10th vs 1/16th s), total dyssynchronization of the pings, and different ping schedules for each ADCP.

Hardware

MCU choice

We use a low-cost, low-power STM32 L031 MCU on a Nucelo-32 evaluation board (NUCLEO-L031K6)¹. This board has a minimal set of peripherals to save power, but includes a few important features:

- 1) Built-in ST-LINK programmer/debugger interface with USB-connection.
- 2) Built-in 24 MHz crystal oscillator, allowing high-precision low-power timer (LPTIM).
- 3) Flexible power supply options – USB, VIN (7–12 V), 5V, 3.3V.

With this choice, we do not need any PCB development or any additional components – just connectors and wiring.

Necessary modification

The NUCLEO-32 board requires one critical modification: Solder bridge SB9 needs to be *removed* (Fig. 4). We power the board using the +5V (CN4 pin 4), which does not provide power to ST-LINK module (which is good – we don’t want to waste power on it). For programming, ST-LINK receives power from USB. Without the ST-LINK running, we need to release the NRST pin of STM32, which is done by removing SB9. This allows STM32 to run without ST-LINK. If SB9 was not removed, STM32 would remain in reset state and *would not run*.

An unintended consequence of removing SB9 is that ST-LINK can no longer reset STM32 before/after programming, so we have to do it manually using the reset button or power-cycling.

We also remove the red PWR LED (LD2) to further save power, but I am not sure it is worth it.

Note that it is possible to power the module using +3.3V power source (CN4 pin 14), which would be more efficient (as it would bypass the 3.3V voltage regulator). To do that, we would need to remove both SB9 and SB14. For this project, we do not have 3.3V power available.

Fig. 4 STM NUCLEO-32 board back-side layout (left) and schematics (right) showing the SB9 solder bridge (red outline) that needs to be removed.

¹ <https://www.st.com/en/evaluation-tools/nucleo-l031k6.html>

Wiring

For the MLF-2 integration, the STM NUCLEO-32 board is soldered to a simple solder breadboard (Fig. 5) that provides mounting points and space for two connectors. MicroUSB connector is also used to connect the on-board ST-LINK programmer to an IE55 connector at the float’s bulkhead.

Connection pinout:

NUCLEO-32 pin	STM32 pin	Wire color	Function
GND (CN4 p2)	-	Black	GND
+5V (CN4 p4)	-	Yellow	+5V
D3 (CN3 p6)	PB0	Green	ADCP#2 RS485 Sync B
D4 (CN3 p7)	PB7	Blue	ADCP#1 RS485 Sync B
D5 (CN3 p8)	PB6	Brown	ADCP#2 RS485 Sync A
D6 (CN3 p9)	PB1	Orange	ADCP#1 RS485 Sync A

(Full wiring diagram is in the Appendix.)

The trigger board is powered from the switched regulated 5VDC power line associated with one of the ADCPs (ADCP#2, MLF COM10). The power is supplied while ADCP#2 is in use.

The trigger board is connected to two ADCPs (#1 and #2) using their RS485 trigger lines (RS485 Sync A/B, Nortek serial connector pins 7/8). Note that we drive synchronization lines *directly* from STM32 GPIO pins, without a RS485 transceiver. Normally, this would not be a good idea since the RS485 protocol requires a 120 Ohm terminator resistor between A/B lines, which might put too much power draw on the GPIO pins. Nortek Signature ADCPs, however, have a 1 nF capacitor in series with the terminator resistor, so there seems to be no danger overloading GPIO pins. If this ever becomes a problem, we can fall back to TTL sync (see below). Either way, including a proper RS485 transceiver is not necessary.

Fig. 5 NUCLEO-32 based “Trigger board” with the external connectors, as deployed on MLF.

To provide differential RS485 trigger signal across the Sync A/B lines, we alternate setting the corresponding GPIO pins high/low:

This satisfies the RS485 standard (min. 1.5 V difference) and actually matches the native trigger signal output by Signature1000 ADCPs.

Note: It would be possible to run Nortek TTL trigger input with minimal modification. Either of the Sync A/B lines (as currently configured) could be used as a TTL sync line (relative to common ground). We choose RS485 synchronization (even though it requires an extra wire) for two reasons: First, our ADCPs are configured with RS485 synchronization by default, so we kept it this way. Second, RS485 may also be preferable for additional noise tolerance.

Trigger scheduling

Similar to the native Nortek ping scheduling, we subdivide each 1-second time interval (“ensemble”) into *N* windows. Nortek uses *N*=16, but we chose to use longer windows (*N*=10). This allows us to space the pings further apart and increases the depth of the previous-ping interference from 47 m to 75 m. We can reconsider this choice, of course.

Since 10 Hz is not a divisor of 32.768 kHz=2¹⁵ Hz, each window is slightly longer than 0.1 s (by 6 μs). This would cause a slow (5 s/day) drift of the ping sequence relative to the real-time clock (RTC). This should not cause any problems, though, since the ADCPs record the actual ping timing using their own RTCs. We just cannot expect pings to occur “on the second” of RTC. If this ever becomes a problem, we can increase *N* to 16 or decrease it to 8 (both are dividers of 32,768).

ADCP ping schedule for one ensemble can be visualized as follows:

Window#	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
+Time (s)	0	.1	.2	.3	.4	.5	.6	.7	.8	.9
ADCP#1	A	B	I	E						
ADCP#2						A	B	I	E	

Here, we configure ADCP#1 to cycle through its 4 ping-sequence (e.g., AVG, BURST, IBURST, ECHO), then, after a 0.1 s delay the same sequence is repeated on ADCP#2. We choose to separate the pings of the two ADCPs in time – although we could alternate them, or even ping synchronously (although this would bring back the problem with the instrument cross-talk).

It is important to match the Trigger Board scheduling to the ping schedule programmed into the ADCPs. When triggered, the ADCP would execute the next ping on *its* schedule; if there is a mismatch between the number of pings in the ADCP and the trigger board schedules, there will be a drift in the actual pings – some ensembles would have more/fewer ping of a particular kind than

expected, which would be inconvenient. Note, however, that the number of pings per ensemble can be *different* for the two ADCPs, as long as the Trigger Board schedule is configured accordingly.

The trigger board cycles through its 1-second ensemble schedule as long as it is powered – with two important exceptions:

- 1) There is a configurable delay (currently set to ~~5~~ 15 s) before the synchronization pings start. The purpose of this delay is twofold: First, it gives time for ST-LINK programmer to connect to STM32, in case we want to change the code. When the trigger cycle starts, connection is refused, likely due to low-power sleep used between the trigger events (see below). Second, it allows both ADCPs to be fully configured and armed before the actual sampling starts. This way, the two ADCPs can start sampling at the same time.
- 2) During the first ensemble, a set of NSTARTUP = 8 trigger pulses is sent to *both* ADCPs using the normal window interval (10 Hz in the above example). This sequence of pings would stand out in the ADCP record(s) and could be used for further alignment of ADCP RTCs. Note that these pings are meant to be *synchronous*, so they may be affected by the interference. We will likely discard them in post-processing.

Thus, a typical startup sequence would look like this:

STM32 configuration and programming

The full STM32 code can be found in the GitHub repository

<https://github.com/shcher2018/stmADCP>.

The schedule is coded as a char array:

```
// Ping schedule for the 2 ADCPs (remember to leave space for \0 terminator)
const char Pings[nADCP][nWindows+1] = {
    // 0123456789
    "XXXXoooooo.",
    "oooooXXXXo."
};
```

Active windows for each ADCP are marked with Xs. During an active window, a sync pulse will be sent to the appropriate ADCP.

During the initialization, we set up a low-power timer (LPTIM) interrupt with an appropriate period counter:

```
HAL_LPTIM_Counter_Start_IT(&hlptim1, round(32768.0/nWindows)-1);
```

This timer drives everything. The main code just puts the STM32 in low power state

```
int main(void)
{
    ... // Initialization

    while (1)
    {
        HAL_PWR_EnterSTOPMode(PWR_LOWPOWERREGULATOR_ON, PWR_STOPENTRY_WFI);
    }
}
```

In the timer callback (HAL_LPTIM_AutoReloadMatchCallback), check if the current window is active for either of the ADCP. If it is, we switch the trigger line states:

```
for(a=0;a<nADCP;a++){
    if (Pings[a][Window] == 'X') {
        // This window is active, toggle the line(s)
        Active = 1;
        pinA_state = HAL_GPIO_ReadPin(GPIOB, pinADCP_RS485[a][0]);
        if (pinA_state==GPIO_PIN_SET){
            HAL_GPIO_WritePin(GPIOB, pinADCP_RS485[a][0],GPIO_PIN_RESET);
            HAL_GPIO_WritePin(GPIOB, pinADCP_RS485[a][1],GPIO_PIN_SET);
        }
        else {
            HAL_GPIO_WritePin(GPIOB, pinADCP_RS485[a][0],GPIO_PIN_SET);
            HAL_GPIO_WritePin(GPIOB, pinADCP_RS485[a][1],GPIO_PIN_RESET);
        }
    }
}
```

(Startup pulses are handled slightly differently.)

The window counter is then incremented.

ADCP configuration

Both ADCPs need to be configured to receive the RS485 trigger pulses:

```
SETTRIG, EN=1, TRIG="RS485EDGES", TRIGOUTPUT=0
```

As discussed above, it is important to match the programmed ADCPs ping sequence with the configuration of the trigger board, i.e. the number of pings requested per 1-second ensemble should match the number of X's in the trigger board configuration scheme.

Operations

The trigger board functions autonomously without any input from the MLF control system – except for the power control.

The trigger board is powered from a regulated +5VDC line associated with ADCP#2. It turns on automatically when ADCP#2 is powered on. Trigger pulses start automatically after a predetermined delay (see above) and continue until the trigger board is powered off.

Processing

In post-processing, we need to detect the startup pings in each instrument's record and use them to align the real-time clocks.

(To be continued)

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Appendix: MLF Trigger Board wiring diagram

MLF 2 ADCP wiring

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